

Phytochemicals with known biological activity identified in the fruit cuticular waxes of introduced *Chaenomeles* plants

Didur Oleh, Khromykh Nina

Oles Honchar Dnipro National University (Dnipro, Ukraine)

Biologically active substances in plant fruits are of interest to consumers due to their potential health benefits, especially for the prevention and counteraction of diseases associated with aging and stress. The fruits of the genus *Chaenomeles* Lindl. species have long been used in traditional medicine, and the modern scientific evidence confirms that they are a rich source of the biologically active compounds [7]. This study provides the identification of bioactive compounds with documented health-promoting properties in the fruit cuticular waxes of *Chaenomeles* species and hybrids introduced to Ukraine (Table 1). (Table 1).

Table 1

Known biologically active phytoconstituents in the fruit cuticular waxes of the genus *Chaenomeles* introduced plants

Compound	Plant species	Biological activity [Literary source]
Oleic acid	<i>Ch. japonica</i> , <i>Ch. cathayensis</i>	Anti-inflammatory, cancer preventive [3]; antimicrobial [18]; antifungal [15]
Linoleic acid	<i>Ch. japonica</i> , <i>Ch. × superba</i>	Antibacterial, antihistamine [4]
Palmitic acid	All studied species	Antioxidant, antifungal [13]; anti-inflammatory [10]
Ethyl palmitate	<i>Ch. japonica</i>	Antioxidant, hemolytic [6]
Diisooctyl phthalate	All studied species	Antimicrobial [14]
Cinnamaldehyde	<i>Ch. × superba</i> , <i>Ch. × californica</i>	Antimicrobial [1]
Myristaldehyde	<i>Ch. speciosa</i> , <i>Ch. × californica</i>	Antimicrobial [17]
Cis-9-Hexadecenal	<i>Ch. cathayensis</i> , <i>Ch. × californica</i>	Antimicrobial [8]
Alpha-Farnezene	<i>Ch. × californica</i>	Antimicrobial [9]
Octacosanol	<i>Ch. japonica</i> , <i>Ch. speciosa</i> , <i>Ch. × superba</i> , <i>Ch. × californica</i>	Anti-parkinsonism [16]
1,3,12-Nonadecatriene-5,14-diol	All studied species	Antifungal [11]
Linalool	<i>Ch. japonica</i>	Antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antitumor, antidepressant and neuroprotective [12]
Olean-12-ene-3,28-diol	<i>Ch. cathayensis</i> , <i>Ch. × californica</i>	Antimicrobial [2]
Lupeol	<i>Ch. cathayensis</i>	Antimicrobial [2]
Urs-12-en-28-al	<i>Ch. cathayensis</i>	Antibacterial, antioxidant [5]

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